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Prevalence of Common Wrist Disorders and Their Associated Risk Factors Among Antepartum Women of Faisalabad: A Cross-Sectional Study**Khadija Asif¹, Shazia Fiaz², Ayesha Sahar³, Iqra Tahir⁴, Kaiynat Shafique⁵, Minahil Atif⁶, Hifza Tahir⁶**

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome, Pregnancy involves numerous physiological changes that may De Quervain's Tenosynovitis, predispose women to various musculoskeletal disorders, including Pregnancy, Risk Factors, Antepartum, wrist pathologies. Among these, Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS), De Compression Neuropathy

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underdiagnosed in antepartum women. The objective of our study was to assess the prevalence of common wrist disorders and identify associated risk factors among second and third trimester antepartum women in Faisalabad. A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted over four months. A total of 120 antepartum women were recruited using non-probability convenience sampling from the gynecological OPDs of Mujahid Hospital, Madina Teaching Hospital, and Faisal Hospital. Diagnosis was based on clinical signs including Tinel's sign, Finkelstein's test, and others. Data were analyzed using SPSS v22; chi-square tests were applied to evaluate associations between wrist disorders and various risk factors. Prevalence rates were as follows: CTS (48.3%), DQT (50%), Wartenberg's Syndrome (46.7%), and Guyon's Canal Syndrome (48.3%). No significant associations were found between wrist disorders and factors like age, BMI, gravidity, or gestational period. However, anemia and pre-eclampsia showed statistically significant associations with CTS ($p < 0.05$). Wrist disorders are highly prevalent among antepartum women, though most demographic and obstetric variables showed no significant link. The significant association of CTS with anemia and preeclampsia highlights the need for preventive screening and early conservative interventions during pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION:

CTS is a frequently occurring condition affecting health that causes sensations of tingling, pain, and loss of feeling in the impacted hand and arm.^[1] CTS occurs when the median nerve becomes compressed or squeezed as it travels through the wrist area. Risk factors for CTS include being overweight, repeat wrist activities, pregnancy, inherited trait, and conditions like rheumatoid arthritis.^[2] CTS sufferers can exhibit various symptoms which are commonly categorized into mild, moderate, or severe type. Typical signs of the condition include pain, a tingling sensation, and numbness along the median nerve pathway. These symptoms may be felt in the thumb, index, middle finger, and the outer portion of the ring finger. Between 4% and 5% of persons globally are thought to have CTS, with older people. Individuals aged 40 to 60 are particularly at higher risk. (Dale et al., 2013) Additionally, females have a higher likelihood of developing CTS compared to males.³

According to more regular assessments of the incidence of CTS, women between the ages of 45 and 54 are more likely to experience it, while males between the ages of 75 and 84 are more at risk.^[4] A widespread issue among manual laborers, CTS is a type of musculoskeletal disorder that is associated with occupational activities in affected individuals. It is brought on by strain and repetitive exercise. Consequently, CTS is often connected to increased complications and higher absenteeism from work. The most prevalent entrapment condition, CTS, affects one or more peripheral nerves, causing the affected body organ to become numb or weak. CTS affects at least 3.8% of people who report having painful, unresponsive, and itching hands on average.⁵

One prevalent wrist pathology is de Quervain's disease, also known as stenosing tenosynovitis of the "initial dorsal section of the wrist". Resisted gliding of these tendons of the short thumb extensor and long thumb abductor muscles in the fibroosseous canal causes pain. Females have a higher risk of developing wrist de Quervain's tenosynovitis. A physical examination may be used to make a diagnosis. Radiographs can be used to rule out bone pathology.^[6] De Quervain's tenosynovitis, a common wrist condition, is also known informally as "mother's thumb" or "gamer's thumb".

Numerous factors can cause Guyon's syndrome, which can lead to injury to the ulnar nerve inside the ulnar canal or elsewhere, which can cause neuropathy in the ulnar nerve segment that travels through the channel. The pressure from outside sources (such as bicycle handle bars), repeated strain from thickened ligaments due to ongoing injuries or tasks, anatomical trauma, or tumors can typically lead to damage in the ulnar nerve, auxiliary muscles, ganglions, or tumors.⁷

There is an increase in work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) in the majority of western countries. This condition is associated with elevated stress and elevated hand movements.^[8] For example, over sixty percent of musculoskeletal conditions in the upper limb have been attributed to occupational factors, in Europe in 1998 were reported to be CTS occurrences. Additionally, the occurrence rates may range among various professions and sectors; for example, the fish processing industry reports that 73% of its employees have CTS. These opinions regarding CTS occurrence rates highlight the severity of the problem and make it a major topic of concern that calls for efficient management techniques. Individuals with early stage or moderately severe CTS are often advised to follow nonsurgical treatment options. Splinting, yoga, physical therapy, corticosteroids, and therapeutic ultrasonography are among the available options. Vitamin B6, diuretics, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications are ineffective treatments.^[9] A local corticosteroid injection can postpone surgery for a year and offer relief for more than a month. Surgical decompression should be an option for patients with severe carpal tunnel syndrome or whose symptoms have not subsided following four to six months of conservative treatment.^[10]

Although endoscopic and open methods are equally effective, endoscopic repair typically allows patients to return to work one week sooner. The application of conservative management was endorsed by another study. Over the course of 10 to 15 months, up to one-third of patients may experience spontaneous improvement in their CTS. The severity determines the available treatments. When the illness is mild to severe, with occasional pain and numbness and no thenar muscle loss or wasting, non-surgical treatment

(splinting or injection) should be taken into consideration.^[11]

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional design was employed for this study. The study setting was gynecological OPDs of these hospitals Mujahid Hospital, Madina Teaching Hospital and Faisal Hospital. The duration of study was 4 months after approval of synopsis. The study population consisted of 18-45 years old second and third trimester antepartum women. The sample size was 120. Non-probability convenience sampling was used in this study. Screening was done based on demographic data including age, BMI, exercise status and pregnancy related risk factors such as gestation duration, number off pregnancies, parity, type of pregnancy (singleton or multiton) and pregnancy-related comorbidities like gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes, hypothyroidism and anemia.

Inclusion Criteria

18-45 year's old women

Second and third trimester prim gravida and multigravida women

Those present at the time of data collection.

Exclusion Criteria

Presence of chronic disorders of hand wrist complex

Presence of any type of degenerative disorder of hand or wrist

Past surgical history of hand or wrist

Any recent trauma or fracture

Each participant was required to sign a consent form before data collection which was provided in both English and Urdu. After signing thee informed consent, demographic data was taken involving age, BMI, exercise status and pregnancy related risk factors such as gestation duration, number off pregnancies, parity, type off pregnancy (singleton or multiple) and pregnancy-related comorbidities like gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes. Tinel's sign (94% specificity) were used to confirm the diagnosis off CTS, Finkelstein's test (specificity 96%, and sensitivity off around 84%) was performed to confirm the diagnosis off DQT.

Tinel's sign over the course off superficial radial nerve was performed to diagnose Wartenberg's syndrome and Tinel's sign (sensitivity 67% and specificity 95%) at the Guyon's canal was used to diagnose Guyon's Canal Syndrome. The data was collected from different hospitals which are mentioned above, we went to the gynecological wards off different hospitals and looked for antepartum women. Total off 200 antepartum females were screened, out of which 80 did not meet thee inclusion criteria and were excluded out of the study. The rest 120 antepartum women who had met thee inclusion criteria were asked questions through our self-made questionnaire and the form was filled by taking their consent. The forms were filled with thee exact information provided by thee subjects and after that specified tests were also applied to check if any signs and symptoms were associated with our conditions.

Results:

Prevalence of common wrist disorder

Figure 1: prevalence of common writ disorder

Association between pre-eclampsia and CTS

Table 1. Chi square test

	Value	df	Asymp. (2-sided)	Sig. Exact (2-sided)	Sig. (2-Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.156^a	1	.013		
Continuity Correction	5.276	1	.022		
Likelihood Ratio	6.229	1	.013		
Fisher's Exact Test				.017	.011
No of Valid Cases	120				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 24.73.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 Table

The above table represents the chi square tests that represents pre-eclampsia and carpal tunnel syndrome have a significant relationship (p-value <0.05) among the antepartum women

Association between anemia and CTS

Table 2. Chi square tests

	Value	df	Asymp. (2-sided)	Sig. Exact (2-sided)	Sig. (2-Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.112 ^a	1	.024		
Continuity Correction	4.313	1	.038		
Likelihood Ratio	5.159	1	.023		
Fisher's Exact Test				.028	.019
No of Valid Cases	120				
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 25.13.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table					

The above table represents the chi square tests that represents anemia and carpal tunnel syndrome have a significant relationship (p-value <0.05) among the antepartum women.

Between exercise frequency and Wartenberg’s syndrome

Table 3. Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.729 ^a	2	.057
Likelihood Ratio	5.879	2	.053
No of Valid Cases	120		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 15.87.			

The above table represents the chi square tests that represents exercise frequency and Wartenberg’s syndrome have a significant relationship (p-value <0.05) among the antepartum women.

Association between exercise type and Guyon’s canal syndrome:

Table 4. Chi-square tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.653^a	5	.040
Likelihood Ratio	12.671	5	.027
No of Valid Cases	120		

a. 2 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

The above table represents the chi square tests that represents that exercise type and Guyon’s canal syndrome does have significant relationship (p-value <0.05) among the antepartum women.

Discussion

The ongoing study purpose is to investigate the occurrence of most common wrist disorders—namely carpal tunnel syndrome and de quervains tenosynovitis, Wartenberg’s Syndrome, and Guyon’s canal Syndrome—among antepartum women, and to identify their association with various maternal risk factors. A total of 120 pregnant women in their second and third trimesters, sampling was done using a non-random convenience approach. This study highlight a high occurrence of wrist pathologies in the antepartum population and provide new insight into the burden and associated risks of such disorders during pregnancy. The study identified a high occurrence of CTS among antepartum women, with 48.3% testing positive through Tinel’s sign. These values are same as previous studies said by Mateen et al. (2024), which reported CTS occurrence rates as high as 46% in pregnant women. Similarly, Oliveira et al. (2019) found occurrence of 23% in their sample, emphasizing the commonality of CTS in pregnancy, particularly in the third trimester due to increased fluid retention, hormonal changes, and pressure on the median nerve. Interestingly, our data found no statistically significant association between CTS and risk factors such as age, BMI, gravidity, parity, or gestational period. However, a significant association was observed with pre-eclampsia (p = 0.013) and anemia (p=0.024). These results indicate that certain pregnancy-related comorbidities, rather than general demographic factors, may be more strongly linked with CTS during pregnancy.

Exactly 50% of thee participants were diagnosed with De Quervain’s Tenosynovitis using Finkelstein’s test, confirming its high rate. In the end our study didn’t found any likelihood between DQT and all examined risk factors.^[12] Although not statistically significant, a near-significant p-value for gravidity (p = 0.073) indicates a potential pattern warranting exploration in future research. The occurrence of Wartenberg’s Syndrome was 46.7%. This condition is underexplored in pregnancy-specific literature. No meaningful correlations were identified between Wartenberg’s Syndrome and any personal or clinical variables, aligning with previous studies that report limited etiological data in antepartum populations.^[13]

Guyon's Canal Syndrome was found in 48.3% of the study population. Despite being considered uncommon in the general population, the high occurrence in this sample highlights the potential under diagnosis in pregnant women. No statistically significant associations were found except a suggestive trend with pre-eclampsia. The occurrence of all four wrist pathologies was found to be between 46.7% and 50%, reflecting a substantial burden of upper limb disorders during pregnancy. Traditional risk factors such as age, BMI, gravidity, and parity showed no significant associations^[14]. Pregnancy-related conditions like pre-eclampsia and anemia were significantly associated with CTS. These findings emphasize the importance of routine screening for musculoskeletal complaints during antenatal care.^[15]

Conclusion

This study concludes that common wrist disorders such as carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS), de quervains tenosynovitis (DQT), Wartenberg's syndrome, and Guyon's canal syndrome are highly prevalent among antepartum women, with occurrence rates ranging from 46.7% to 50%. The findings highlight that pregnancy-related comorbidities like preeclampsia and anemia have a significant association with CTS, while other demographic and obstetric variables such as age, BMI, gravidity, parity, and type of pregnancy showed no significance. These results emphasize the clinical need for early identification and routine screening of wrist disorders during antenatal care to enhance maternal comfort and prevent long-term disability. The findings also underscore the importance of adopting multidisciplinary strategies involving physiotherapists, obstetricians, and occupational therapists.

Limitations

The study was investigated using non probability sampling, which may introduce selection bias.

The sample size of 120 limits generalizability to the broader antepartum population.

Only second and third trimester women were included; thus, first trimester conditions remain

Diagnosis was based solely on physical examination without using the imaging tests which may question the diagnostic accuracy.

Strengths

This study is among the few that comprehensively assessed multiple wrist pathologies simultaneously in a pregnant population.

A structured methodology and standardized clinical tests (Tinel's, Finkelstein's) were used to ensure consistent data collection.

Ethical standards were rigorously followed, and the study covered diverse hospital settings, increasing relevance.

Recommendations:

Routine Screening: Implement routine wrist screening protocols during antenatal visits, especially in the mid and late stages of pregnancy to identify symptoms early.

Education and Awareness: Educate pregnant women about the signs and symptoms of wrist disorders and promote ergonomic practices in daily activities.

Multidisciplinary Management: Encourage collaboration between physiotherapists, gynecologists, and occupational therapists to provide comprehensive care.

Non-surgical Interventions: Promote conservative management strategies such as wrist splinting, activity modification, and physical therapy as first-line interventions.

Further Research: Conduct longitudinal studies to track postpartum progression of symptoms and assess treatment outcomes.

Policy Development: Advocate for inclusion of musculoskeletal assessments in maternal health policies to ensure broader implementation across healthcare settings.

Conflict of Interest: None

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Authors Contributions:

KA, SF, AS and IT contributed to conception and design. KA, SF, AS contributed to data acquisition. KA, SF, AS, IT and KS contributed to data analysis. MA and HT contributed to article drafting and revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors approved the version of manuscript to be published.

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